

In ovo phage administration to mitigate *Salmonella* Typhimurium colonization in broiler chickens – A new firewall strategy for the poultry industry

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ABSTRACT

Hatcheries, as the initial stage of the poultry production pipeline, play a pivotal role in the potential spread of *Salmonella*. The high-density rearing conditions of industrial poultry production, coupled with the routine transfer of chicks from hatcheries to multiple farm locations, heighten the likelihood of pathogen dissemination across wide geographic areas. Therefore, there is a need for innovative disinfection strategies that align with regulatory requirements and effectively target pathogenic threats. In this context, this study aimed to assess the safety and efficacy of bacteriophages application *in ovo* as a preventive measure to mitigate *Salmonella* transmission from hatcheries to the rearing farms. To do so, two experiments were conducted. Experiment 1 evaluated the safest and most effective *in ovo* inoculation site for phage delivery, while the Experiment 2 tested the efficacy of a phage cocktail administered via the amniotic liquid in reducing *Salmonella* Typhimurium colonization during the first 21 days post-hatch after direct and indirect exposure. The results demonstrated that phage administration in the amniotic liquid was the safest and most suitable *in ovo* inoculation site. Furthermore, phage treatment significantly reduced *Salmonella* colonization in directly infected chicks and completely prevented transmission in indirectly exposed birds. *In ovo* administration of the phages proved to be a promising prophylactic firewall strategy to limit the spread of *Salmonella* within the production chain.

1. Introduction

Salmonella is a Gram-negative bacterium from the Enterobacteriaceae family and a core member of the microbiome of different domestic animals (Nair et al., 2013; Rothrock et al., 2024). Among *Salmonella enterica* species, non-typhoidal *Salmonella* strains typically cause no symptomatology on poultry, while severe and life-threatening cases are described in human infections (Eng et al., 2015; Wilson et al., 2000). *Salmonella* infection can occur by direct contact or by the consumption of contaminated water or food (Hoelzer et al., 2011). As *Salmonella* foodborne outbreaks (FBO) in humans are frequently linked to poultry

product consumption, the poultry sector has implemented control measures to mitigate its impact, serving as safety barriers between animals and consumers (E. EFSA, 2021; EFSA & ECDC, 2023). Nevertheless, *Salmonella* caused more than 200 outbreaks in the European Union (EU) in 2022 and 2023, and around 52 multi-state outbreaks in the USA alone in 2022 (CDC, 2024; EFSA & ECDC, 2023, 2024). Furthermore, it is estimated that non-typhoidal *Salmonella* strains are responsible for the largest number of gastroenteritis cases and hospitalizations globally, with approximately 93 million cases and 155,000 fatalities annually, posing a substantial global public health challenge (Chlebicz & Sliżewska, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2024).

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The presence of *Salmonella* in poultry farms entails a direct public health risk due to the potential human consumption of contaminated food products. However, its presence in other facilities within the production system can pose an even greater danger to food safety (Chlebicz & Slizewska, 2018; Knodler & Elflein, 2019). As the starting point of the poultry production chain, hatcheries act as important reservoirs for *Salmonella* dissemination (Rothrock et al., 2024; Zamil et al., 2021). The intensive nature of production systems and the cross-movement of chicks from the hatcheries to farms exacerbate this risk, enabling the spread of *Salmonella* across geographically distant regions. This broad-scale dissemination throughout physically separated territories has a global impact on both animal and human health (Rothrock et al., 2024; Van Steenwinkel et al., 2011; Wales & Davies, 2020). Despite the implementation of cleaning and disinfection protocols, prophylactic protocols and good biosecurity measures, cross contamination between batches frequently occurs, facilitating the widespread dissemination of *Salmonella* (Rothrock et al., 2024). Residual eggshell fragments or chick fluff from previous batches infected with *Salmonella* can persist on hard-to-disinfect surfaces such as chick conveyor belts or equipment, leading to continuous *Salmonella* infection of different batches (Zamil et al., 2021). Although current and forthcoming regulations on antimicrobial substances in animal production aim to enhance food safety, they simultaneously limit the prophylactic and control tools available to producers (Gundersen et al., 2023; Ruvalcaba-Gómez et al., 2022). In that sense, the development of novel strategies that effectively combat pathogens while complying with those regulations is urgently needed in the poultry sector (Ruvalcaba-Gómez et al., 2022). Non-antibiotic-based approaches, particularly those targeting critical control points such as hatcheries, are essential to curbing *Salmonella* dissemination and mitigating its impact across the production chain.

Bacteriophages, or phages, are re-emerging as promising alternatives to conventional prophylactic and therapeutic agents for the control of bacterial infections. They represent one of the safest options for the prevention, treatment, and eradication of bacterial pathogens, including multidrug-resistant (MDR) (Gundersen et al., 2023; Hyman, 2019; Rehman et al., 2019). Unlike antibiotics, phages exhibit high host specificity, minimizing off-target effects such as disruption of the commensal microbiota (Gundersen et al., 2023). Additionally, phages can be evolved *in vitro* to overcome the potential emergence of bacterial resistance to phages, one of the main limitations historically associated to phage therapy, thereby enhancing their long-term efficacy as a targeted alternative to antibiotics (Peters et al., 2024). The use of phages as therapeutic agents, known as phage therapy, has been explored at various stages of poultry production, primarily focusing on the control of *Salmonella* in rearing animals and on environment of production facilities (Sevilla-Navarro et al., 2024; Sevilla-Navarro et al., 2024). However, despite the promising results obtained in these settings, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding the application and effectiveness of phages for controlling *Salmonella* contamination within hatcheries.

Thus, the development of new strategies against *Salmonella* is vital to reduce its economic impact on the poultry industry and to limit its spread from hatcheries to downstream farms. Therefore, the main objectives of this study were, first, to identify the best *in ovo* inoculation site and evaluate the safety of a phage-based prophylaxis against *Salmonella*, and second, to assess the efficacy of a cocktail of bacteriophages as an early prophylactic intervention following *in ovo* administration in broilers.

2. Material and methods

The animal procedures were conducted in accordance with the protocol approved by the Directorate-General for Agriculture, Fisheries, and Livestock of the Valencian Community (research code: 2023-VSC-PEA-0037).

To achieve the stated objectives, the study was divided into two experiments: **Experiment 1** - Phage inoculation site and safety

assessment, and **Experiment 2** – *In vivo* phage efficacy trials.

2.1. Experiment 1 - phage inoculation site and safety assessment

2.1.1. Phage propagation

The bacteriophage selected to evaluate the inoculation site and its stability was vB_cecav_048, a *Skatevirus* morphologically compatible with a *Siphovirus*, previously characterized (Torres-Boncompte et al., 2025). The propagation strain (PS) of the phage was a *Salmonella enterica* subsp. *enterica* serovar Typhimurium monophasic var. Copenhagen field strain from the poultry industry.

The phage was propagated in 450 mL of Luria-Bertani (acc. Miller) (LB) (Sharlab) broth inoculated with 5 mL of its propagation strain at an optical density (OD₆₀₀) of 0.2 (~10⁸ CFU/mL). The phage was added at a multiplicity of infection of 0.01 to the bacterial culture. After a 4-h incubation at 37 °C with shaking at 200 rpm, the lysate was centrifuged at 8000×g for 5 min and sequentially filtered through 0.45 µm and 0.2 µm PES filters (VWR - Avantor). Subsequently, an aliquot of the lysate underwent serial dilutions and was plated using the double-layer agar (DLA) method to determine phage titers in triplicate (Kutter, 2009). Then, 150 mL of the lysate were concentrated to 10 mL through ultrafiltration using Macrosep Advance Centrifugal Device 100 K (Pall®), and the buffer switched from LB to 1 × Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) (0.14 M NaCl, 0.0027 M KCl and 0.01 M PO₄³⁻, pH 7.4), as previously described by Bonilla et al., 2016. The concentration process involved loading 15 mL of lysate at a time into a vertical filter system and performing repeated centrifugation cycles. After loading phage solution, the process involved repeated centrifugation cycles (4000×g for 5 min at 4 °C) until the entire 150 mL volume was processed. To ensure complete buffer exchange, five additional centrifugation cycles were performed with 1x PBS. Once the lysate appeared clear, was added to adjust the final volume was adjusted to 10 mL with 1x PBS, and the sample was vortexed to release retained phages. The resulting high-titer phage preparation was filtered (0.22 µm, PES) and quantified using the DLA method before being stored at 4 °C until use.

2.1.2. Incubation conditions and egg handling

A total of 113 Specified Pathogen-Free (SPF) embryonated eggs were obtained from VALO BioMedia GmbH (Salamanca, Spain). All SPF eggs were incubated at 37 °C with 55 % relative humidity (RH), rotating 90° every 90 min for 18 days (Fig. 1). On day 18, they were transferred to the hatcheries and set under static conditions at 37 °C and 70 % RH, until hatching occurred between days 21 and 22.5 (Fig. 1) (Aviagen, 2009, 2022). On days 8 and 18, the eggs were inspected through candling to discard any non-developing eggs. Discarded eggs were refrigerated at 4 °C for 1 h and examined to determine whether the cause of failure was due to embryonic death or non-fecundated eggs.

2.1.3. Phage *in ovo* application

By day 18, before transference, the viable eggs were divided between three experimental groups for *in ovo* inoculation site testing: air cell (AC), amniotic liquid (AmL) and allantoic fluid (ALF). To evaluate the impact and safety of the technique and the phage administration on the embryos, each inoculation site group was further divided into two subgroups: a phage-inoculated group (φ-group), and a group inoculated with 1 × PBS (PBS-group). Additionally, a control group (C-) with non-manipulated embryonated eggs, where neither phage nor PBS was inoculated, was included.

All egg inoculation procedures were performed in a biosafety level II (BSL-II) microbiological safety cabinet. For the *in ovo* inoculations, egg surfaces were disinfected with wipes impregnated with an alcoholic solution of 70 % ethanol, followed by air drying at room temperature for 5 min. Access to the interior of the eggs was achieved by piercing the eggshell on the air cell using 18 G × 1" sterile needles (1.2 × 25 mm). All *in ovo* site groups were inoculated with 0.1 mL of the phage at ~10⁹ PFU/mL (~10⁸ PFU/egg) employing appropriately sized needles to

Fig. 1. Egg incubation cycle (days), conditions and handling (Created in <https://BioRender.com>).

ensure accurate site inoculation (Table 1) (Peebles, 2018; Roto et al., 2016).

The access points for the AC and ALF eggs were centered through the eggshell on the air cell, while for AmL eggs, the access point was distal (Fig. 2A), aiming not to reach the body of the embryo (Fig. 2C, D & E respectively). To properly inoculate the phage in the AmL, the eggs were candled through the AC, and then the head of the embryo, perceived as an outstanding structure through the opaque shadow the embryo projected on the eggshell, was delineated (Fig. 2B). The lower boundary of the AC that was above the head of the embryo was also marked, and lastly, perpendicular to both previous marks an access point was established in the AC (Fig. 2B). After inoculation, the access point on the eggshell was sealed with tempered liquid paraffin at 50 °C and left to solidify for a couple of minutes before the eggs were introduced into the hatcheries.

2.1.4. Phage safety assessment

Phage safety on the embryonated eggs and the non-hazardousness of the procedures were evaluated by analyzing the hatching rates of the experimental groups. The hatching rates were calculated with the following formula: hatching rate (%) = (number of hatched eggs/total number of eggs in the group) × 100. In this context, all unhatched eggs after day 22.5 were further inspected, and only embryonic deaths were considered. On one hand, to assess phage safety within each inoculation site, the embryonic death counts of each φ-group was compared to its corresponding PBS-group and the C- group. On the other hand, to assess the non-hazardousness of the employed procedures, the embryonic death counts of each inoculation site, including the cumulative counts of the φ-group and PBS-group, were compared to the C- group.

2.1.5. Phage stability and colonization

The persistence and distribution of the phage within the egg were evaluated by detecting and quantifying phages in cloacal swabs and cecum samples. Phage colonization capacities in the environment after hatch were assessed through phage detection and quantification in hatch-generated debris, such as chick fluff and eggshells. All phage titers

Table 1
Technical specifications of the *in ovo* inoculation techniques.

Inoculation site	Inoculation needle	Needle approach	References
Air Cell	25 G (0.5 × 18 mm)	Tip of the needle in the AC though the access point.	(Peebles, 2018; Roto et al., 2016)
Amniotic Liquid	23 G (0.6 × 25 mm)	Wholly introduced at a 90° angle from the access point.	
Allantoic Fluid	21 G (0.8 × 40 mm)	Wholly introduced at a 90° angle from the access point.	

Fig. 2. *In ovo* inoculation sites and approaches. A: eggshell access points from an upper view of the egg. B: exterior delineation of the interior structures of the 18-day embryo for an AmL inoculation. C: sagittal view of the AC inoculation. D: sagittal view of the ALF inoculation. E: sagittal view of the AmL inoculation (Created in <https://BioRender.com>).

were measured in triplicate using the DLA method.

Cloacal swabs were collected individually after hatching to sample the meconium. Each swab was immersed in 2 mL of Buffered Peptone Water (BPW) (VWR - Avantor) for 15 min, followed by thorough vortexing. The resuspended sample was centrifuged to 8000×g for 5 min and filtered through 0.22 μm PES syringe filters. On day 1 of life, individual cecum samples were taken from the chicks, diluted 1:10 (w:v) with BPW, and vigorously homogenized. A 2 mL aliquot of each sample was recovered, centrifuged at 8000×g for 5 min and filtered through 0.22 μm PES syringe filters.

Before transferring the eggs to the hatcheries, sheets of vegetal paper were placed below the hatching trays, and after day 22.5 they were gathered and used as environmental samples. The samples were soaked in enough BPW to saturate the contents and vigorously homogenized. Then, a 2 mL aliquot was recovered, centrifuged at 8000×g for 5 min, and filtered through 0.22 μm PES syringe filters.

2.2. Experiment 2 – In vivo phage efficacy trials

The efficacy of *in ovo* phage application as a prophylactic tool was evaluated under two different *Salmonella* infection conditions:

- **Experiment 2.1:** Evaluation of phage efficacy in 1-day-old chicks orally infected with *Salmonella*.
- **Experiment 2.2:** Indirect evaluation of phage efficacy during the production cycle, under *Salmonella* infection from environmental sources.

2.2.1. Egg incubation and handling

To test the efficacy of the *in ovo* phage administration against both indirect and direct *Salmonella* infection in the production cycle, 132 eggs (Ross) were obtained from a commercial supplier. The eggs were incubated and monitored as previously described in Experiment 1.

2.2.2. Bacteriophage production and cocktail assembly

Phages vB_cecav_041, vB_cecav_048 and vB_cecav_050, previously characterized by Torres-Boncompte et al. (2025) targeting *S. Typhimurium*, were used for the efficacy trial (Torres-Boncompte et al., 2025). The lytic capacity of these phages was further evaluated against the challenge strain (CS) and PS used in this experiment through efficiency of plating assays (EOP) and kinetic growth curve analyses. Both methods were performed as described by Torres-Boncompte et al., 2025. The *Salmonella* CS used for the study was a spontaneous rifampicin resistant (Rif^R) mutant of *S. Typhimurium* ATCC14028, previously employed in animal colonization (Colom et al., 2015, 2017). The PS used for phage propagation was *S. Typhimurium* LB5000 (SGSC181; University of Calgary).

All phages were scaled up to a volume of 150 mL, followed by centrifugation (8000×g 15 min) and sequential filtration through 0.45 µm and 0.22 µm PES filters. The titers of individual phages were quantified using the DLA method. Phages were concentrated to ~10¹⁰ PFU/mL, and the buffer was exchanged for 1 × PBS through ultrafiltration using a Macrosep Advance Centrifugal Device 100 K, as previously described in Experiment 1. Then, a phage cocktail was prepared by combining equal parts (1:1:1) of each phage, and its lytic activity was characterized through EOP against the PS and CS strains (Torres-Boncompte et al., 2025).

2.2.3. Phage administration

On day 18, prior to transfer, viable eggs were divided into two groups. Following the procedures described in Experiment 1 for A/mL phage inoculation, one group was inoculated with the phage cocktail at a dose of 10⁹ PFU/egg. Animals hatched from this group on day 22.5 were assigned to the *Salmonella* and phage treatment (φ+S) group for Experiment 2.1, and the Treatment (φ) group for Experiment 2.2 (Table 2). Meanwhile, the second group of eggs, which did not undergo

Table 2
Experimental group distribution of Experiment 2.

	Group	Phage-inoculated	<i>Salmonella</i> infection	Pens (n)
Experiment 2.1	<i>Salmonella</i> Control (S)	–	Direct – Orally at day 1 of the production cycle	4
	Treatment (φ+S)	<i>In ovo</i> , day 18 of incubation	Direct – Orally at day 1 of the production cycle	4
Experiment 2.2	Treatment (φ)	<i>In ovo</i> , day 18 of incubation	Indirect – Environmental	1
	Control (C)	–	Indirect – Environmental	1

n: number of pens per experimental group.

in ovo inoculation on day 18, served as the *Salmonella* Control (S) group for Experiment 2.1 and the Control (C) group for Experiment 2.2 (Table 2).

2.2.4. Housing and growth conditions

Once hatched, the experimental groups were placed into two identical poultry houses. For Experiment 2.1, the pens directly infected with *Salmonella* (S and φ+S) were placed in different houses. In Experiment 2.2 indirect *Salmonella* infection was achieved by housing the C group pen in the same house as the S pens, maintaining a 4 m distance between them. Similarly, the φ+S pens were housed 4 m away from the φ pen within the same house (Suppl. Fig. 1). The number of chickens per pen was established after the hatching period to ensure equal distribution among pens and experimental groups.

The animal trial was conducted at an experimental poultry farm located at the Center for Research and Animal Technology (CITA-IVIA, Centro de Investigación y Tecnología Animal, Segorbe, Spain). The animals were handled according to standard practice in poultry production (Aviagen, 2020). The poultry houses were supplied with wood shavings as bedding material, programmable electrical lights, automated electric heating systems and forced ventilation. The environmental temperature was gradually reduced from 32 °C on the day of arrival to 22 °C by 21 days post-hatch.

2.2.5. *Salmonella* challenge strain and chicken infection

In Experiment 2.1, direct *Salmonella* infection of animals was performed in the S and φ+S groups on day 1 of the production cycle. To do so, the *Salmonella* CS was recovered from CECAV’s repository (–80 °C) and cultured on LB agar. Following overnight incubation at 37 °C, biomass from the plate was suspended in 1x PBS to achieve an OD₆₀₀ of 0.2 (~10⁸ CFU/mL). Then, serial 1:10 dilutions with 1x PBS were performed to prepare a final suspension with an estimated concentration of 10⁵ CFU/mL. Animals were orally infected with 0.1 mL of this suspension, attaining a final dose of 10⁴ CFU/animal. Bacterial titers of the suspensions used for chick inoculation were verified by serial dilution and plating on Xylose-lysine-deoxycholate agar plates (XLD) (Sharlab, Barcelona) supplemented with 75 mg/L rifampicin (Sharlab, Barcelona).

In Experiment 2.2, indirect *Salmonella* infection was achieved in the C and φ groups through environmental contamination within the housing units. Rigorous biocontrol workflows were followed in housing facilities to prevent iatrogenic contamination of the C and φ groups with *Salmonella* CS.

2.2.6. *Salmonella* colonization on experiment 2.1

To evaluate the efficacy of the *in ovo* phage application in directly infected animals, *Salmonella* colonization was monitored on the environment (boot swabs) and in animals (cecum samples). Boot swabs from the S and φ+S groups were collected on days 2, 3, 7, 14, and 21 post-infection. Cecum samples were taken from S and φ+S on days 2, 3, 7, and 21 for *Salmonella* enumeration (Fig. 3A). All samples underwent *Salmonella* enumeration analysis.

Salmonella enumeration was performed as previously described by Sevilla-Navarro, Otero, et al. (2024) (Sevilla-Navarro et al., 2024). Initially, boot swabs were diluted in 225 mL of BWP per pair of boot swabs, and cecum samples were diluted 1:10 (w:v) in BWP, and 100 µL of each dilution was plated on XLD plates supplemented with 75 mg/L rifampicin. Black colonies on the surface of the media after an overnight incubation at 37 °C were counted and CFU/mL assessed.

2.2.7. *Salmonella* colonization on experiment 2.2

At the beginning of the rearing cycle, on day 1, 4 cecum samples from each group (C and φ), were collected to verify the *Salmonella*-negative status of the pens. Then, *Salmonella* colonization in the non-infected pens (C and φ), was monitored through its detection using boot swabs. To that aim, samples were taken on days 2 and 3 of the production cycle and at the end of each week (days 7, 14, and 21) (Fig. 3B). Additionally,

Fig. 3. Sampling chronograms of the rearing period (days). A: sampling chronogram for Experiment 2.1., direct *Salmonella* infection. B: sampling chronogram for Experiment 2.2., indirect *Salmonella* infection (Created in <https://BioRender.com>).

at the end of the cycle, all ceca were sampled to assess *Salmonella* colonization in the animals.

Salmonella detection was performed following the ISO 6579:2017. To this end, all samples underwent an initial dilution with BPW, 225 mL per pair of boot swabs and 1:10 (w:v) per cecum samples. Following overnight incubation at 37 °C, cultures were seeded onto Modified Semi-solid Rappaport-Vassiliadis (MSRV) (bioMérieux, France) agar and incubated for 48 h at 41 °C. Plates showing whitish growth around the inoculation points were reseeded onto two chromogenic media, ASAP™ (bioMérieux, France) and XLD. Purple colonies on ASAP or black colonies on XLD, after an overnight incubation at 37 °C, were identified as *Salmonella*.

2.2.8. Bacteriophage detection and enumeration

The boot swabs and intestinal cecum gathered for *Salmonella* detection and enumeration on Experiments 2.1 and 2.2 were also processed for phage detection and enumeration. In brief, an aliquot from the initial dilution of the boot swabs and cecum samples was recovered, centrifuged at 8000×g for 5 min and filtered through a 0.22 μm PES syringe filter. Then, 10 μL of each sample were laid onto bacterial lawns of the CS, and the PS for phage detection through the DLA method. Samples testing positive for phage presence underwent further phage enumeration through serial dilutions on DLA plates.

2.2.9. Analysis of *S. Typhimurium* variants with reduced phage-susceptibility

Detection of *Salmonella* CS isolates with reduced susceptibility to the applied bacteriophages (vB_cecav_041, vB_cecav_048, and vB_cecav_050) was conducted using boot swabs and cecum samples from Experiment 2.1. Following sample processing, a total of 720 colonies from the cecum samples of S and φ+S groups were analyzed (120 colonies per group and sampling day: 3, 7, and 21). Regarding boot swabs, a total of 862 colonies were evaluated (120 colonies per group and sampling day: 3, 7, 14, and 21), except for day 3 in the φ+S group, where only 22 colonies were recovered. Randomly selected colonies were streaked onto LB agar plates supplemented with Rif (75 mg/L) and incubated at 37 °C for 18 h. Afterwards, colonies underwent at least two consecutive subcultures to ensure the absence of concomitant bacteriophages in the culture.

To assess the susceptibility to vB_cecav_041, vB_cecav_048, and vB_cecav_050 phages, the selected *Salmonella* CS isolates were cultured in LB liquid medium, in the presence of each phage, in 96-well microtiter plates (Sterilin™, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA). The plates were incubated at 37 °C with shaking at 500 rpm, and the growth was monitored by measuring OD₆₀₀ every hour for 5 h using the plate reader Sunrise (Tecan Trading AG, Switzerland). The parental *Salmonella* CS was included as a control. Isolates exhibiting OD₆₀₀ values over time similar to those of the uninfected control cultures were categorized as isolates with reduced-susceptibility to the phages, whereas those showing decreasing OD₆₀₀ values, due to the lysis promoted by the phage, were classified as sensitive to phages.

Due to inconclusive results in microtiter plate assay, susceptibility to the bacteriophage vB_cecav_041 was determined by spot assay. In this case, fifty randomly isolates from the ceca and boot swabs of each group and sampling day were analyzed, except for day 3 of the φ+S group boot swabs, where only 22 colonies were recovered. Each isolate was tested by spotting 5 μL of serial tenfold dilutions of phage lysate (ranging from 1 × 10⁷ to 1 × 10³ PFU/mL) onto double-layer LB agar plates containing the isolate, following the DLA method. Plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C. The parental *Salmonella* CS was used as sensitive control. Isolates exhibiting a significant decrease in bacteriophage titer compared to the control were classified as having reduced susceptibility.

2.3. Statistical analysis

The hatchability rates obtained in the experiments were analyzed with Fisher's exact test, based on the number of hatched and unhatched eggs displayed in contingency tables. The significance level of *p*-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All quantification assays for *Salmonella* and phage titers were performed in triplicate, with results expressed as mean ± standard deviation in log₁₀ CFU/mL and PFU/mL, respectively. Statistical analysis of titers was performed using a two-way ANOVA, followed by Šidák's multiple comparisons test, with a *p*-value ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant. All analyses and graphical representations were carried out with GraphPad Prism 10 (MA, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Experiment 1 - phage inoculation site and safety assessment

3.1.1. Incubation conditions and egg handling

After candling all 113 eggs on day 8 of the incubation cycle, 23 eggs (20.35 %) were removed from the incubators. Of these, 9 exhibited signs of embryonic death (7.96 %) and the other 14 of being non-fecundated eggs (12.40 %). On day 18, prior to phage inoculation, the remaining 90 eggs were candled again, and no additional eggs with signs of embryonic death were detected. Consequently, each experimental group was composed of 12 eggs, except for the C- group, which contained 18 eggs (Table 3).

3.1.2. Phage safety and procedures' non-hazardousness

In the evaluation of phage vB_cecav_048 safety, significant differences were observed only between the hatching rates of φ-AIF, C-AIF and C- (*p-value* = 0.043), but no other differences were appreciated between groups per each inoculation site (*p-value* > 0.05) (Table 3). Moreover, in the evaluation of the inoculation procedure, no statistically significant differences were found between the hatching rates from each inoculation site when compared to the C- group rates (*p-value* > 0.05) (Table 3).

3.1.3. Phage stability and colonization

Phage vB_cecav_048 was detected in the 57.14 % (4/7) of the cloacal swabs from φ-AC, 50.00 % (4/8) from φ-AmL and 42.86 % (3/7) from φ-AIF, and no significant differences (*p-value* > 0.99) were observed (Fig. 4A). The average phage titers (PFU/sample) were $4.93 \pm 1.03 \log_{10}$ for φ-AC, $4.67 \pm 0.70 \log_{10}$ for φ-AmL, and $5.10 \pm 0.89 \log_{10}$ for φ-AIF, with no significant differences between them (*p-value* > 0.05) (Fig. 4B).

In cecum samples, phage detection rates were 87.50 % (7/8) in φ-AmL, 85.71 % (6/7) in φ-AIF and 57.14 % (4/7) in φ-AC, with no significant differences between groups (*p-value* = 0.45) (Fig. 4A). However, significant differences were observed concerning the average phage titers (PFU/sample). Being, $4.98 \pm 0.44 \log_{10}$, $4.65 \pm 0.55 \log_{10}$ and $3.66 \pm 0.30 \log_{10}$, for φ-AmL, φ-AIF and φ-AC, respectively (*p-value* < 0.05) (Fig. 4B).

From the environmental samples, only the debris from the φ-AC tested positive for phage detection, with an average phage titer of $6 \log_{10}$ (PFU/sample) (Fig. 4A and B).

3.2. Experiment 2 – bacteriophage in ovo administration efficacy trials

3.2.1. Bacteriophage production and cocktail assembly

The selected phages vB_cecav_041, vB_cecav_048, and vB_cecav_050, exhibited EOP values ≥ 0.95 on both the PS and CS when tested on DLA plates. Additionally, their lytic capacities on the CS (individually and as a cocktail) on liquid media were confirmed through kinetic growth curves (Suppl. Fig. 2).

Table 3

Egg distribution through experimental groups and unhatched eggs per group.

Group	Phage inoculation	Inoculation technique									
		N	Hatched		Unhatched		N	Hatched		Unhatched	
			n	%	n	%		n	%	n	%
Air Cell	φ-AC	12	7	58.33 %	5	41.67 %	24	18	75.00 %	6	25.00 %
	C-AC	12	11	91.67 %	1	8.33 %					
Amniotic Liquid	φ-AmL	12	8	66.67 %	4	33.33 %	24	17	70.83 %	7	29.17 %
	C-AmL	12	9	75.00 %	3	25.00 %					
Allantoic Fluid	φ-AIF	12	7	58.33 %	5	41.67 %	24	19	79.17 %	5	20.83 %
	C-AIF	12	12	100.00 %	0	0.00 %					
Control	C-	18	14	77.78 %	4	22.22 %	18	14	77.78 %	4	22.22 %

N: number of eggs per experimental group. n: number of eggs in each situation. AC: air cell. AmL: amniotic liquid. AIF: allantoic fluid. C-: control group.

3.2.2. Egg incubation and rearing cycle

Out of the 132 eggs incubated at the beginning of the trial, 16 were discarded between days 8 and 18 after candling due to embryonic death and showing signs of being a non-fecundated egg (Supplementary Table 1). The overall hatchability rate for the incubation cycle was 81.82 %, with 108 out of 132 hatched eggs (Fig. 5). For the phage-inoculated eggs, the hatching rate was 96.97 % (64 out of 66), while the non-inoculated eggs had a hatching rate of 88.00 % (44 out of 50), with no significant differences between the two groups (*p-value* > 0.05) (Supplementary Table 1) (Fig. 5).

During the rearing cycle, only three animals died of natural causes. All of these belonged to pens from group φ+S and were found between days 7 and 14 (Suppl. Table 1).

3.2.3. Salmonella colonization on experiment 2.1

Boot swabs samples from the S pens tested positive for *Salmonella* at every sampling timepoint, with 4/4 samples per day, and 20/20 positive samples throughout the cycle. The average *Salmonella* concentration (CFU/mL) in this group throughout the cycle was $6.26 \pm 0.80 \log_{10}$, with no significant differences between titers across sampling days (Fig. 6A). In contrast, in the φ+S group, 85 % (17/20) of the boot swabs were positive compared to S group throughout the whole cycle. The lowest concentrations were registered on day 2 of the rearing cycle, where 75 % (n = 3/4) of the boot swabs had levels below the limit of detection (<2 log₁₀). After day 7, the *Salmonella* concentration slightly increased, reaching an average of $4.16 \pm 0.84 \log_{10}$, with minor statistical differences between sampling points (Fig. 6A). Notably, the values from φ+S were statistically lower than those in the S group throughout the production cycle, with a reduction of at least 2 log₁₀.

Regarding cecum samples (Fig. 6B), 100 % of them (32/32) in the S group tested positive to *Salmonella* throughout the cycle, with an average concentration (CFU/mL) of $7.66 \pm 0.61 \log_{10}$, showing no significant differences between sampling points. In contrast, in the φ+S group, 3 out of 41 samples fell below the detection threshold (<2 log₁₀), on days 2, 3, and 21. The lowest *Salmonella* concentration was appreciated on day 2 in the φ+S group, with an average value of $3.18 \pm 0.87 \log_{10}$. Although concentrations increased after day 2 in the φ+S group, they remained significantly lower than those in the S group throughout the production cycle, with a reduction of at least 2.5 log₁₀.

After assessing the efficacy of *in ovo* phage administration in the φ+S during the first week of rearing, the phage cocktail was given to the animals on days 13th and 20th. To do so, 0.1 mL of phage cocktail at 10¹⁰ PFU/mL was administered orally to the animals from φ and φ+S (10⁹ PFU/chicken).

3.2.4. Salmonella colonization on experiment 2.2

None of the cecum samples from day 1 tested positive for *Salmonella*, confirming that the animals were *Salmonella*-free at the beginning of the rearing cycle. The conversion of pens to *Salmonella*-positive status in the φ and C groups was tracked through *Salmonella* detection in boot swabs. In the C group, *Salmonella* was consistently detected from day 2 until the

Fig. 4. Phage detection and quantification results. A: phage detection rates (%) per group. B: interleaved scatter of the phage titers on phage-positive sample per phage inoculated group. ^{ab}: indicates significant differences between groups (p -value ≤ 0.05). φ-AC: air cell phage inoculated group. φ-AmL; amniotic liquid phage inoculated group. φ-AIF: allantoic fluid phage inoculated group.

Fig. 5. Hatchability rated from Experiment 2.

end of the trial. However, in the φ group, detection was intermittent, occurring only on days 3, 14, and 21. At the end of the 21-day-rearing cycle, cecal samples were analyzed for *Salmonella* presence, and while in the C group, 100 % of the samples (8/8) were positive, in the φ group none (0/16) tested positive (p -value < 0.05).

3.2.5. Bacteriophage detection and enumeration on experiment 2.1

Phages were detected in 100 % (4/4) of the boot swabs samples from φ+S at each sampling timepoint, with all 20/20 samples testing positive. Phage titers presented no relevant variations between timepoints when enumerated with both the *Salmonella* PS and CS (Fig. 7A).

Similarly, phages were detected in 100 % (41/41) of the cecum samples from φ+S. In this regard, the titers obtained with *Salmonella* PS and CS were 4.21 ± 1.19 and 4.03 ± 1.48 log₁₀(PFU/mL), respectively (Fig. 7B). The titers obtained with both strains remained stable throughout the trial, with no statistically significant differences between timepoints (p -value ≤ 0.05) (Fig. 7B).

Fig. 6. *Salmonella* concentration in directly infected animals (Experiment 2.1.). A: *Salmonella* concentration (CFU/mL) in boot swabs during the 21-day rearing cycle. B: *Salmonella* concentration (CFU/mL) in cecum samples during the 21-day rearing cycle. ^{ab}: superscripts indicate statistical similarities between concentrations (p -value ≤ 0.05).

Fig. 7. Box diagram of phage titers on φ+S (Experiment 2.1.). A: phage titers (log₁₀(PFU/mL)) from boot swab samples. B: phage titers (log₁₀(PFU/mL)) from cecum samples. * Indicates statistical differences between titers (p -value ≤ 0.05).

3.2.6. Bacteriophage detection and enumeration on experiment 2.2

Phages were detected in 100 % (5/5) of the boot swabs samples from ϕ at each sampling timepoint. Enumeration obtained with *Salmonella* PS and CS enlightened that the phage titers in the environment increased from day 2–3, and then gradually decreased until the end of the cycle, reaching 2 and 1 log₁₀ (PFU/mL) respectively (Fig. 8A).

Regarding phage titers on cecum samples no significant differences were observed between titers in the ϕ group on day 2 and day 21 (*p*-value \leq 0.05) (Fig. 8B).

3.2.7. Detection of ATCC14028 Rif^R variants with reduced phage-susceptibility on experiment 2.1

All *Salmonella* CS isolates from boot swabs in the S and ϕ +S groups, collected on days 3, 7, 14, and 21, remained sensitive to the three phages that composed the administered cocktail. However, isolates with reduced phage susceptibility were exclusively recovered from cecal samples in the ϕ +S group (Table 4). On day 3, three isolates exhibited reduced susceptibility: 1 out of 120 isolates showed reduced susceptibility to all three phages in the cocktail, 1 out of 120 to vB_cecav_050, and 1 out of 50 to vB_cecav_041. On day 7, 2 out of 50 isolates displayed reduced susceptibility to vB_cecav_041.

Overall, in cecal samples of the ϕ +S group, three *Salmonella* CS isolates out of the 150 analyzed (2 %) exhibited reduced susceptibility to vB_cecav_041, while one out of 360 isolates displayed reduced susceptibility to vB_cecav_050 (0.3 %), and one out of 360 to the three phages of the cocktail (0.3 %) (Table 4).

4. Discussion

Hatcheries represent one of the most critical control points in the poultry production chain (Shterzer et al., 2023). As centralized hubs where eggs from multiple breeding flocks and diverse origins converge, hatcheries constitute an environment with high microbial load and increased risk of pathogen dissemination (Shterzer et al., 2023). Among these pathogens, *Salmonella* is of particular concern due to its ability to be vertically transmitted through the eggshell and its widespread impact on both animal and public health (Lei et al., 2020; Pan & Yu, 2013). Formaldehyde has historically been used in hatcheries to minimize the bacterial load of eggs and to modulate microbial bloom in the environment for more than 100 years, yet its use has come under stricter regulations in the EU due to its proven carcinogenic properties (Ricke et al., 2019; Selby et al., 2023). Though its use is not completely banned in hatcheries (Ricke et al., 2019), it is highly regulated and controversial, highlighting the need for safer alternatives to conventional biocontrol strategies in the sector. Given the sensitivity of this stage and the need to implement preventive measures early in the production cycle, the *in ovo* method has emerged as a valuable strategy for the uniform and efficient application of vaccines and other biologically active agents directly into the egg (Li et al., 2023).

Bacteriophages have gained increasing attention as effective biocontrol agents against a range of bacterial pathogens, including MDR

strains (Jamal et al., 2019; Subramanian, 2024). However, despite their demonstrated efficacy at later stages of poultry production, research exploring their application during the hatchery phase, particularly via *in ovo* administration, remains limited. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that assess and demonstrates the efficacy of *Salmonella*-specific phages administered *in ovo* for the control of *S. Typhimurium* colonization in chickens.

In the present study, different *in ovo* inoculation sites were assessed. While no major differences in phage detection were observed across the groups, phages were successfully detected in cecum samples, indicating effective diffusion into the embryonic structures (Fig. 4A). AIF and AmL administrations presented the highest concentration of phage in cecum samples, with no statistical differences between them. These results align with previous findings, where a phage cocktail against *Escherichia coli* was detected in 88 % of chicks after phage was inoculated into the AIF (Nicolas et al., 2023). However, ϕ -AIF administration presented significantly reduced hatching rates, underscoring AmL as the fairest option to offer protection against *Salmonella* in subsequent production stages, particularly on farms where the chicks are transferred after hatching, which is also the most common site for other vaccine applications (Peebles, 2018). Nonetheless, significant differences were observed in the detection of phages in environmental samples taken from the hatchery, where phages were only detected in samples from the group inoculated in the air cell (ϕ -AC group). These findings are particularly interesting, as although the phages were detected in 57 % of the animals from the AC group, their presence in the hatchery environment is noteworthy. Notably, from the three *in ovo* sites tested for phage administration, the AC is the only embryonic structure that is not absorbed or consumed by the embryo during its development (Givisiez et al., 2020). Though the structure itself reduces in size as the embryo grows, it is still present at after hatch and therefore is still present in the hatcheries' environment as part of the hatching debris (Givisiez et al., 2020). Given that chicks can remain several in hatching trays for several hours post-hatch, the persistence of phages in the environment—stemming from inoculation via the air cell—could provide additional protection against *Salmonella* from contaminated materials or hatchery facilities (Gast et al., 2024; Rothrock et al., 2024). The different spreading dynamics observed in the three administration sites suggest the potential for a more targeted protection against *Salmonella*, allowing the choice of inoculation site to be based on the specific phase of the rearing cycle where the protection against *Salmonella* needs to be enhanced.

Following *Salmonella* challenge at one day of age, the results of this study demonstrate the efficacy of phages applied *in ovo* to protect broiler chickens from *S. Typhimurium* colonization. In the direct challenge trial, the phage-treated group (ϕ +S) showed a substantial reduction in *Salmonella* loads during the first two days post-infection: from approximately 6 to 2 log₁₀ CFU/mL in boot swabs, and from 8 to 3 log₁₀ CFU/mL in cecal samples (Fig. 6). From day 7 onward, *Salmonella* levels in the ϕ +S group remained consistently 2 log₁₀ CFU/mL lower than in the untreated infected group (S), a difference that was maintained

Fig. 8. Phage titers on Experiment 2.2. A: phage titers (log₁₀(PFU/mL)) on boot swabs. B: phage titers (log₁₀(PFU/mL)) on cecum samples. ^{abc}: Superscripts indicate statistical similarities between titers (*p*-value \leq 0.05).

Table 4ATCC14028 Rif^R variants with reduced susceptibility to vB_cecav_041, vB_cecav_048, and vB_cecav_050 phages isolated from Experiment 2.1 samples.

Sample	Time (day)	S - group				φ+S - group			
		No. reduced-susceptibility variants/total analyzed isolates ^a				No. reduced-susceptibility variants/total analyzed isolates ^a			
		041	048	050	041 + 048+050	041	048	050	041 + 048+050
Boot swabs	3	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120	0/22 ^b	0/22	0/22	0/22
	7	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120
	14	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120
	21	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120
Ceca	3	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120	1/50	0/120	1/120	1/120
	7	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120	2/50	0/120	0/120	0/120
	21	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120	0/50	0/120	0/120	0/120

^a From each sampling day and sample type, 120 isolates were tested with vB_cecav_048 (048), and vB_cecav_050 (050) phages, and 50 isolates were studied with vB_cecav_041(041) phage.

^b All colonies that grew on count plates were tested.

throughout the study period. Notably, this protective effect was achieved without compromising embryo viability, as no significant differences in hatching rates were observed between phage-treated and non-inoculated groups across all experiments (Fig. 5). These results are consistent with previous studies that reported no adverse effects of phage administration on animal safety (Nicolas et al., 2023).

It is well established that *Salmonella* colonization in broilers peaks within the first 21 days of the rearing cycle, a period during which animals gradually develop immunocompetence, contributing to a natural reduction in pathogen burden (Wang et al., 2024). Therefore, the early *in ovo* administration of phages effectively mitigates *Salmonella* colonization in both animals and their environment during this critical vulnerability window. Moreover, the emergence of phage-resistant *Salmonella* strains was minimal, with only 0.3 % of isolates exhibiting reduced susceptibility to the phage cocktail, and these were detected exclusively in the cecum of φ+S animals. This low incidence of variants with reduced susceptibility likely contributed to the sustained efficacy of the treatment, underscoring the potential of phage therapy as a sustainable and robust antimicrobial strategy for controlling *Salmonella* infections (Sevilla-Navarro et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the efficiency of *in ovo* phage administration to prevent horizontal *Salmonella* transmission was evaluated in experiment 2.2. By the end of the experiment, 100 % of the animals in group C tested positive for *Salmonella*, whereas none (0 %) of the animals in the φ group became infected. As horizontal pathogen transmission is a major concern for pathogen spread between animal batches on farms (Byrd et al., 1998; Gast et al., 2014; Jarosinski et al., 2007; Liljebjelke et al., 2005), these results are highly promising, suggesting that early *in ovo* administration of phages may effectively prevent *Salmonella* transmission. In contrast, boot swab samples tested positive for *Salmonella* at the end of the trial in both groups. This could likely be attributed environmental contamination, possibly through dust, rather than direct excretion by animals in the φ group, as both groups were housed in the same environment (Gole et al., 2014; Rodriguez et al., 2006; Skóra et al., 2016).

Overall, the results of this study provide compelling evidence supporting the use of *in ovo* phage administration as a promising strategy to control *Salmonella* colonization in chickens. The early application of phages not only resulted in a significant reduction of bacterial load in both the animals and their environment during the most susceptible period of the production cycle, but also showed a minimal emergence of phage-resistant variants. These findings underscore the potential of this novel phage therapy approach as a complementary or alternative tool to conventional antimicrobial interventions, particularly in light of increasing concerns over antibiotic resistance.

Despite the proved efficacy of the technique towards *S. Typhimurium*, the high specificity that phages have to their host would oblige for tailored phage cocktail preparations to attain protection towards specific *Salmonella* strains (Gundersen et al., 2023). This specificity

highlights the value of maintaining well-curated phage repositories with diverse and well-characterized candidates for rapid deployment (Peters et al., 2024; Torres-Boncompte et al., 2025). Additionally, strategies aimed at isolating phages with broad host ranges or designing multi-host cocktails further enhance the versatility of phage applications (Hyman, 2019). In the context of poultry hatcheries, such specificity can be advantageous, as it reduces the risk of disrupting beneficial microbiota transmitted from breeders to broilers, microorganisms that play a key role in establishing a healthy gut environment (Gundersen et al., 2023; Wales & Davies, 2020). Nevertheless, further research is needed to evaluate the long-term effects of this approach under commercial conditions, its efficacy against other *Salmonella* serovars, and its integration into broader biosecurity and management programs within poultry production systems.

5. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive investigation of a novel phage therapy approach for the poultry industry, yielding promising results. Both the phage cocktail and its individual phage components demonstrate strong potential as effective therapeutic agents for controlling *S. Typhimurium* in poultry. The absence of significant adverse effects associated with this technique highlights its immediate applicability within current biocontrol strategies used in the poultry industry. As a One-Health-oriented firewall strategy, these approach holds considerable promise for limiting the spread of *Salmonella* from multiple sources, thereby reducing the economic burden on the poultry industry and mitigating public health risks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Torres-Boncompte: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Josep Garcia-Llorens:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Pilar Cortés:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Anna Martínez-Sánchez:** Methodology, Investigation. **Montserrat Llagostera:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Susana Campoy:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **José M. Soriano:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Pablo Catalá-Gregori:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources. **Sandra Sevilla-Navarro:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2025.111637>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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